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**MACEDONES, PERSIA
ET ULTIMA ORIENTIS**

**Alexander's Anabasis from the Danube
to the Syr Darya**

Edited by Marek Jan Olbrycht and Jeffrey D. Lerner
in collaboration with Michał Podrazik

CONTENTS

ISSUE 1: MACEDONES, PERSIA ET ULTIMA ORIENTIS

Franca Landucci (Italy)	
Alexander, the Crown Prince	9
Sabine Müller (Germany)	
Alexander and Macedonian Relations with Thebes – A Reassessment	21
Luisa Prandi (Italy)	
Byzantium and Alexander the Great: A Convergence of Interests	40
Nicholas Victor Sekunda (Poland)	
Alexander and Demaratus of Corinth at the Battle of the River Granicus	47
Silvia Panichi (Italy)	
Alexander and Cappadocia	62
Marek Jan Olbrycht (Poland)	
Alexander the Great in Sittakene and the Reorganization of his Army (331 B.C.)	80
Waldemar Heckel (Canada)	
Artabazos in the Lands Beyond the Caspian	93
Jeffrey D. Lerner (USA)	
Alexander's Settlement of the Upper Satrapies in Policy and Practice	110
Eduard V. Rtveladze (Uzbekistan)	
Alexander the Great's Campaign in Basand (Baisun)	129
Luis Ballesteros Pastor (Spain)	
Zopyrion's Scythian Campaign: Historical and Historiographical Problems	142
Tomasz Ślęczka (Poland)	
An Ambiguous Hero: Alexander of Macedon in Old Polish Literature: Selected Aspects	160

ISSUE 2: VARIA ASIATICA

Altay Coşkun (Canada)

The Liberation of Judaea and Early Maccabaeen Diplomacy with Rome according to Justin (36.3.9), Diodorus (40.2/4) and Caesar (Jos. *Ant. Jud.* 14.10.6 [205]) 181

Andrea F. Gatzke (USA)

Bilingualism and the Monumental Landscape in the Triodos of Ephesos 204

Eduard Rung (Russia), Aleksandr Sapogov (Russia)

The Aftermath of the Peace of Callias 227

Jeffrey D. Lerner (USA)

Die Studies of Six Greek Baktrian and Indo-Greek Kings 236

THE HISTORY OF SCHOLARSHIP

Joanna Pisulińska (Poland)

History of the Middle and Far East in the Studies of Scholars in Lwów (1918–1939) 249

Alexander A. Sinitsyn (Russia)

Frolov's Torch: The Russian Historian of Antiquity is LXXXV 278

REVIEWS

Jeffrey D. Lerner (USA)

Pavel Olegovich Novik, *Sardoba Maverannahra (po marshrutnym issledovaniiam)* [П.О. Новик, *Сардоба Мавераннахра (по маршрутным исследованиям 2015–2017 гг.)*], Tashkent: Baktria Press 2017 289

Nicholas Victor Sekunda (Poland)

Geoff Lee, Helene Whittaker, Graham Wrightson (eds.), *Ancient Warfare: Introducing Current Research, Vol. I*, Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing 2015 291

Abbreviations 295

Marek Jan Olbrycht
(Rzeszów University, Poland)

Peter Funke in Dankbarkeit
und Freundschaft gewidmet

ALEXANDER THE GREAT IN SITTAKE NE AND THE REORGANIZATION OF HIS ARMY (331 B.C.)

Keywords: Alexander the Great, Iran, military, Sittakene, infantry, Persis, Uxian land, Babylonia

The Reinforcements from the Balkans

After departing from Babylon, his force strengthened with European reinforcements, Alexander conducted military reforms in Sittakene (Curt. 5.2.1-2; Diiod. 17.65.2-4; Arr. *An.* 3.16.10-11).¹ On the fertile plains of Sittakene within the boundaries of present-day Khuzestan, Alexander gave the troops a few days' rest (December 331 B.C.).

Curtius sets the arrival of the reinforcements in Babylon (5.1.40-42), while Diodoros (17.65.1) on the march to Susa. Arrian (*An.* 3.16.10-11) relates both reinforcements and reforms to Susiana. In fact, there is no fundamental contradiction in the sources because the reinforcements may have arrived in parts, but they were enrolled in the army in Sittakene. It is worthwhile to consider these three descriptions, which differ significantly in the location of the events. Arrian, so praised by many as a "sober" author, is wrong to write about the location at Susa. The location of reorganization in Sittakene by the Vulgate authors is precise. Arrian repeatedly misunderstood the location of events and made many mistakes in these matters. Indeed, reinforcements from Europe may have arrived back in Babylon (as stated by Curtius), but Alexander would have had difficulty introducing the reorganization in the big, newly subjugated city, where stationing a large

¹ Alexander's reforms in Sittakene: Bosworth 1980, 319-321; 2010, 92-93; Atkinson 1987; 1994, 57-62; Hammond 1981, 164-5; 1983, 142; Sekunda 1998, 43; 2007, 333; Hatzopoulos 1996, 444-452; Daniel 1991; Olbrycht 2004, 111, 122, 125; 2007; 2011; English 2009, 31-35.

army must have caused some provisioning headaches. The luxury and amenities of Babylon contributed to the downfall of discipline in Alexander's army, tired of heavy fighting. Besides, Alexander tried to avoid any repressive measures to win the favor of the Babylonians. At the same time, it may be supposed that he did not quite feel secure in such a huge metropolis as Babylon, which required a vast military potential to keep under control; any rebellion could have shattered the Macedonian forces. By contrast, Sittakene was a rich, fertile country abounding in provisions of all sorts (Diod. 17.65.2; Curt. 5.2.3). The time and place were the most favorable for the reorganization of the army. Temperatures at this season, i.e. in December, were moderate. The king knew that Susa was devoid of Persian military cover and that he could feel safe in Sittakene. After Gaugamela, Alexander had sent one of his officers, Philoxenos, to accept the surrender of Susa (Arr. *An.* 3.16.6).

The reinforcements were brought by Amyntas, son of Andromenes (Arr. *An.* 3.16.10).² The troops consisted of 6,000 foot soldiers and 500 cavalry from Macedonia, 3,500 foot soldiers and 600 horsemen from Thrace, 4,000 foot soldiers and 380 horsemen from Peloponnese, and 50 sons of Macedonian nobles (Curt. 5.1.39-41).³ Diodoros 17.65.1 reports similar units which "Antipater sent to Alexander"; but gives "little less than 1,000 cavalry from Peloponnese."⁴

Aims of the Reorganization

Reform of the armed forces was made necessary by new military challenges and a different theater of operations to come. For the first time, Alexander was to tread on the soil of Iranian heartland, a mountainous land of the Zagros where the Macedonian phalanx in its regular shape could at best play a secondary role. At that juncture, emphasis had to be placed on missile troops, including javeliners and archers, other types of light infantry, and overall mobility of the entire force. At

² και τούτω ἔδωκεν ἀργυρίου τάλαντα ἐς τρισχίλια φέρειν ἐπὶ θάλασσαν, καὶ ἀπ' αὐτῶν ἀποστεῖλαι παρ' Ἀντίπατρον ὅσων ἂν δέηται Ἀντίπατρος ἐς τὸν πρὸς Λακεδαιμονίους πόλεμον. ἐνταῦθα καὶ Ἀμύντας ὁ Ἀνδρομένους ζὺν τῇ δυνάμει ἀφίκετο, ἦν ἐκ Μακεδονίας ἦγε.

³ *Inter haec flagitia exercitus ille domitor Asiae per XXXIII dies saginatus ad ea, quae sequebantur, discrimina haud dubie debilius futurus fuit, si hostem habuisset. Ceterum quo minus damnum sentiret, identidem incremento renovabatur. Namque Amyntas Andromeni ab Antipatro Macedonum peditum VI milia adduxit, D praeterea eiusdem generis equites, cum his DC Thracas adiunctis peditibus suae gentis III milibus D et ex Peloponneso mercennarius miles ad III milia advenerat cum nongentis octoginta equitibus.*

⁴ τοῦ δὲ βασιλέως ἀναφεύξαντος ἐκ τῆς Βαβυλῶνος καὶ κατὰ τὴν πορείαν ὄντος ἦκον πρὸς αὐτὸν παρὰ μὲν Ἀντιπάτρον πεμφθέντες ἵππεις μὲν Μακεδόνες πεντακόσιοι, πεζοὶ δὲ ἑξακισχίλιοι, ἐκ δὲ Θράκης ἵππεις μὲν ἑξακόσιοι, Τραλλεῖς δὲ τρισχίλιοι καὶ πεντακόσιοι, ἐκ δὲ Πελοποννήσου πεζοὶ μὲν τετρακισχίλιοι, ἵππεις δὲ βραχὺ λείποντες τῶν χιλίων, ἐκ δὲ τῆς Μακεδονίαστῶν φίλων τοῦ βασιλέως υἱοὶ πενήκοντα πρὸς τὴν σωματοφυλακίαν ὑπὸ τῶν πατέρων ἀπεσταλμένοι.

one point, Alexander ordered the soldiers to use a “half-cuirass” (*hemithorakion*) protecting the front part of the torso, instead of full torso armor (Polyain. 4.3.13). This probably happened in Sittakene prior to the planned campaign in the mountains of western Iran. It seems that the infantry of the phalanx was trained in two types of combat, as heavy infantry with strong protective equipment, and as light infantry. The same soldier was able to fight as a light or heavy infantryman for the Macedonian infantry became multifunctional: Macedonian foot soldiers were, at times, armed as heavy hoplites,⁵ but were able to operate as light foot soldiers too.⁶ Some units specialized in fighting as light troops, like the battalion (*taxis*) of Koinos which fought against, among others, the Mardians (Arr. *An.* 3.24.1) in 330, and the Assakenians (Arr. *An.* 4.25.6) in 327/6. A select corps of light infantry was formed by the Hypaspists. In his pursuit of Darius III in Parthia, Alexander used “the strongest and lightest of the infantry” (Arr. *An.* 3.21.2). These infantry units were Hypaspists under Nikanor and Agrianes under Attalos.⁷ The general trend during the fighting in Asia was to reduce the weight of infantry and cavalry protective armor.⁸

Alexander partly altered the structure of military units and enhanced rivalry of those pursuing of command positions. At that time, he did not yet have native Iranian units on his side and had to rely solely on troops he had brought from Europe. The principal intentions of the reorganization are given by Diodoros 17.65.2-4,⁹ who focuses on Alexander’s efforts to promote new commanders and to strengthen the forces by the number, and stresses that Alexander conducted the reforms to improve the effectiveness of his army “looking toward the battles to come” (17.65.4). Apparently, Alexander realized that the impending wars in Iran would require increased mobility and combat power.

⁵ The Macedonian Koragos had heavy armor, a javelin, a sword, and a long spear in his combat against Dexippos in 326/5 (Curt. 9.7.16-26; Diod. 17.100.1-101.6). He is an example of a heavy infantryman. Also, cf. the description by Polyainos 4.2.10 with Olbrycht 2010, 99.

⁶ Juhel 2017, 66.

⁷ Arr. *An.* 3.21.8 with Milns 1978, 377.

⁸ Olbrycht 2004, 100-102.

⁹ Diod. 17.65.2-4: [2] ὁ δὲ βασιλεὺς τούτους παραλαβὼν προῆγε καὶ κατήνησεν ἑκταῖος εἰς τὴν Σιττακινὴν ἐπαρχίαν. τῆς δὲ χώρας ταύτης πολλὴν ἀφθονίαν ἐχούσης τῶν ἐπιτηδείων πάντων ἐν ταύτῃ πλείους ἡμέρας ἔμεινεν, ἅμα μὲν σπεύδων ἐκ τῆς κατὰ τὴν ὁδοιορίαν ταλαιπωρίας ἀναλαβεῖν τὴν δύναμιν, ἅμα δὲ τῆς στρατιωτικῆς τάξεως διανοοῦμενος ἐπιμεληθῆναι καὶ τὰς ἡγεμονίας ἀναβιβάσαι καὶ τὴν δύναμιν ἰσχυροποιῆσαι τῷ τε πλήθει καὶ ταῖς ἀρεταῖς τῶν ἡγεμόνων. [3] συντελέσας δὲ τὰ δεδογμένα καὶ μετὰ πολλῆς ἐπιμελείας περὶ τῶν ἀριστίων κρίσιν ποιησάμενος καὶ πολλοὺς ἀπὸ τῆς μεγάλης ἡγεμονίας ἐπὶ μεγάλας ἐξουσίας ἀναβιβάσας πάντας τοὺς ἡγεμόνας εἰς ἀξίωμα μεῖζον καὶ στοργὴν ἰσχυρὰν πρὸς ἑαυτὸν προήγαγεν. [4] ἐπεμελήθη δὲ καὶ τῆς ἰδιωτικῆς τῶν στρατιωτῶν διατάξεως καὶ πολλὰ πρὸς τὴν εὐχρηστίαν ἐπινοησάμενος ἐπὶ τὸ κρεῖττον διορθώσατο. κατασκευάσας δὲ πᾶσαν τὴν στρατιάν εὐνοία τε πρὸς τὸν ἡγούμενον διαφέρουσαν καὶ πρὸς τὰ παραγγελλόμενα πειθαρχοῦσαν, ἔτι δὲ ταῖς ἀνδραγαθίαις ὑπερβάλλουσαν ἐπὶ τοὺς ὑπολειπομένους ἀγῶνας ὥρμησεν.

Reforms

Alexander decided to reorganize the cavalry in Sittakene. By that time, the Companion cavalry (*hetairoi*) was divided into squadrons called *ilai*, mobilized on a territorial-tribal basis.¹⁰ The number of the Companion *ilai* was eight at the beginning of the Asian war, and the Companions numbered about 1,800, commanded by Philotas (Diod. 17.17.4, 17.57.1; Arr. *An.* 3.11.8).¹¹ Casualty figures of the Companion cavalry up to winter 331/330 must have amounted to about 1,000 men killed or incapacitated for further action. The number is, of course, approximate.¹² Alexander assigned the newly arrived horsemen from Macedonia to the Companion cavalry (Arr. *An.* 3.16.11) to replenish the losses. Counting on the attested reinforcements of 800 horsemen in 333 and 331, Alexander could at best make up for losses and transfers, or perhaps – if the reckoning of losses is exaggerated – slightly increase the strength of the Companion cavalry in Sittakene to up to about 2,000 men.¹³ In Sittakene, Alexander also received 50 sons of Macedonian nobles who were to serve as his bodyguards (Diod. 17.65.1; Curt. 5.1.42). It is possible that they were later enrolled in the Companions.

In the course of the Sittakene reforms, Alexander divided each cavalry squadron (*ile*) into two companies (*λόχοι*). Arrian (*An.* 3.16.11) underscores that there had formerly been no cavalry companies (*λοχοί*). As company commanders (*lochagoi*), Alexander appointed men distinguished for their courage. An analogous criterion to that of the infantry commanders (*chiliarchoi*) can be seen here. The reform mostly affected Macedonian Companions, who had to be subdivided into units smaller than squadrons in order to be effective in a variety of combinations – with footmen and other cavalry units.

Arrian (*An.* 3.16.10-11) underscores that the troops brought from Macedonia were assigned to the Companion Cavalry, and attached to the foot battalions “in accordance with their tribal origin” (κατὰ ἔθνη).¹⁴ Curtius 5.2.6 remarks: *Nam cum ante equites in suam quisque gentem describerentur seorsus a ceteris, exempto nationum discrimine praefectis non utique suarum gentium, sed delectis attribuit.*¹⁵

¹⁰ Griffith in Hammond / Griffith 1979, 411.

¹¹ Domaszewski 1926, 33-34; Sekunda 1998, 21; Rzepka 2008, 46-50 gives six units of the “territorial” Companions and a Royal Squadron (*ile basilike*).

¹² Hammond 1998, 409-414; Aperghis 1997, 136-7; Olbrycht 2004, 95-96, 110-113.

¹³ Olbrycht 2004, 94, 122, 125.

¹⁴ Arr. *An.* 3.16.11: καὶ τούτων τοὺς μὲν ἰππέας ἐς τὴν ἵππον τὴν ἑταιρικὴν κατέταξεν Ἀλέξανδρος, τοὺς πεζοὺς δὲ προσέθηκεν ταῖς τάξεσι ταῖς ἄλλαις, κατὰ ἔθνη ἐκάστους ξυντάξας. κατέστησε δὲ καὶ λόχους δύο ἐν ἐκάστη ἴλι, οὐ πρόσθεν ὄντας λόχους ἰππικούς, καὶ λοχαγοὺς ἐπέστησε τοὺς κατ’ ἀρετὴν προκριθέντας ἐκ τῶν ἑταίρων. Cf. Hatzopoulos 1996, I, 451-2; Rzepka 2008.

¹⁵ “formerly, cavalrymen were enrolled in separate units according to their nationality, but he (Alexander - MJO) now abolished tribal distinctions and gave command of the units to men of his own choosing without regard to race”. Transl. Yardley.

This description should be understood as that in some units the tribal criterion was abandoned and the commanders were changed. Apparently, the statement of Curtius refers to commanders who were appointed without regard to ethnic origin (*gens*). According to the *communis opinio*, the Companion cavalry and the phalanx were recruited on a territorial-tribal basis by the districts of Lower and Upper Macedonia.¹⁶ Actually, the ethnic principle in recruiting soldiers still played an essential role for we hear, for example, of Bactrians and Sogdians fighting in Koinos' corps in Sogdiana next to the Companions, *hippakonstistai* and "the other troops" in 328 (Arr. *An.* 4.17.3). Furthermore, the *hetairoi* were to include more and more Iranians from 330 on. But Curtius stresses that the commanders were chosen without regard to their ethnic origin.

Concerning the Macedonian infantry, the number of soldiers in battalions called *taxeis* was about 1,500 each hitherto.¹⁷ A part of the infantry units was called the *pezhetairoi*, whereas choice units were designated as the *asthetairoi*.¹⁸ The *asthetairoi* formed three τάξεις or battalions of 1,500 men, that is, half of the phalanx that Alexander led to Asia. They usually fought as units with lighter equipment in operations such as climbing, mountain combat, and pursuing the enemy.¹⁹

Curtius (5.2.2-5) gives a detailed description of a reform carried out by Alexander in his infantry:

Itaque diutius ibi substitit, ac, ne desides otio demitterent animos, iudices dedit praemiaque proposuit de virtute militari certantibus nova: qui fortissimi iudicati essent, singulis militum milibus praefuturi erant, - chiliarchas vocabant, - tunc primum in hunc numerum copiis distributis: namque antea quingenariae cohortes fuerant, nec fortitudinis praemia cesserant. Ingens militum turba convenerat egregio interfutura certamini, testis eadem cuiusque factorum et de iudicibus latura sententiam: quippe verone an falso honos cuique haberetur, ignorari non poterat. Primum omnium, virtutis causa, donatus est Adarrhias senior, qui omissum apud Halicarnason a iunioribus proelium unus maxime accenderat, proximus ei Antigenes visus est, tertium locum Philotas Augaeus obtinuit, quartus Amyntae datus, post hos Antigonos, et ab eo Lyncestes Amyntas fuit, septimum locum Theodotus, ultimum obtinuit Hellanicus. [ed. Hedicke].

According to this account, Alexander created units of a thousand men called *chiliarchiai* (χιλιαρχίαι), each composed of two sub-units of 500 men. The infantry

¹⁶ See, e.g., soldiers from Lynkos and Orestis forming a single *taxis* (Diod. 17.57.2; Curt. 4.13.28). For a detailed discussion, see Milns 1976, 103-105; Hatzopoulos 1996 I, 451-2 with references.

¹⁷ The best treatment of the organization of the Macedonian infantry (including phalanx and light units), which also envisages the division of each *taxis* of *pezhetairoi/asthetairoi* into three *lochoi* of 500 (or more accurately 512) is that of Milns 1976, 101-102. Cf. Berve 1926, I, 115; Griffith in Hammond / Griffith 1979, 414-431; Sekunda 1998, 27-42.

¹⁸ *Asthetairoi*: Anson 2010.

¹⁹ See the convincing insights of Noguera Borel 1997, 215-32. Anson 2010 offers another view (he fails to cite Noguera Borel 1997) arguing that the *asthetairoi* were named for their shields decorated with the "star" emblem.

had formerly been divided into units of 500 soldiers (Curtius calls them *cohortes*), probably named *lochoi* (the term is attested later in Arr. *An.* 4.2.1) for the military campaign in Sogdiana in 329) or *pentakosiarchiai*. Both *chiliarchoi* and *pentakosiarchoi* are attested as military commanders in the later army of Alexander (Arr. *An.* 7.25.6; Plut. *Alex.* 76.6).

The New Commanders (*chiliarchoi*)

New unit commanders (*chiliarchoi*) were chosen for their bravery – Curtius (5.2.2-4) gives the names of these newly appointed officers. Arrian (*An.* 3.16.11) states that Alexander appointed as *lochagoi* men distinguished for courage among the Companions. A textual problem arises at Curtius 5.2.2, as the writer names eight persons awarded by Alexander with the position of commander of a thousand – *chiliarchos*. But his enumeration is preceded by a disputable account in which the word *novem* – attested in manuscripts – was emended by Hedicke and others into *nova* as an epithet of *praemia*. If the form *novem* is retained, the text implies nine winners, but the list consists of only eight names. The emendation from *novem* to *nova* gives a coherent text: prizes were of “a new kind”, as the passage mentions new awards in the military competition, and these awards are high-ranking command posts, i.e. *chiliarchiai*. Any emendation is a contentious interference in the text, but in this case the correction seems justified.²⁰ Leaving *novem* in place necessitates a far more dubious emendation in the list of winners, because one name is missing. In other words, *novem* implies a considerable lack in the text of Curtius and the need for significant interference. It is possible to point to other omissions in Curtius and his negligence concerning some details,²¹ but in the case discussed here Hedicke’s emendation in his old Teubner edition (1908) is less intrusive and explains the historical message much more accurately. It is doubtful that the list of eight new chiliarchs is Curtius’ error, especially since it partly coincides with the names given by Plutarch (*Mor.* 339B).

Curtius’ account implies that *chiliarchoi* were new commanding posts. However, there are references implying the existence of units called *chiliarchiai* among the Hypaspists (*hypaspistai*), i.e. the royal elite infantry, in the Macedonian army before the Sittakene reform. Adaios was styled *chiliarchos* of the Hypaspists well before the Sittakene reforms in 334 and the same pertains to Timander (Arr. *An.* 1.22.4, 1.22.7).²² It seems therefore that the Hypaspists had formed units called chiliarchies prior to the reforms in Sittakene, unlike the remaining parts of the army.

²⁰ This textual problem discusses Atkinson 1987, 415-420. The editions of Müller / Schönfeld 1954, and Lucarini 2009, retain *novem*.

²¹ Atkinson 1987, 416.

²² See Rzepka 2008, 43, n. 9.

Some scholars maintain that Arrian's mentions of chiliarchs is an anachronistic use of the designation introduced later due to Arrian's sloppiness.²³ This is basically possible, but a different explanation seems more likely: the Hypasists' corps was organized earlier, perhaps even under Philip II, according to the thousand-system, and the Persian guard was the likely model. In Sittakene, the royal guard of the Hypaspists was not reorganized. Later on, Nearchos and Antiochos are termed chiliarchs of the Hypaspists (Arr. *An.* 4.30.5-6. Cf. 3.29.7, 5.23.7). Arrian (*An.* 4.24.10) speaks of a "third of the Hypaspists" in 327-6 which implies a threefold division of the guard. This implies the existence of three units – *chiliarchiai*, each totaling at 1,000 men, in the Hypaspists' corps.

An analysis of the above-mentioned list of victors in Curtius is difficult because of repetitive Macedonian names there.²⁴ The first three names Curtius gives are those of Atarrhias (= Adarrhias), Antigenes, and Philotas of Augaia. Plutarch supplies the same names.²⁵ Atarrhias may have been the Hypaspist officer who appeared in charge of the "police" troops that arrested Philotas at Phrada in 330 (Curt. 6.8.19-22). He played an active role in the case of Alexander Lynkestes, too.²⁶ Atarrhias thus seems a close associate of Alexander after 331. Antigenes was probably one of the Hypaspist commanders at the Hydaspes in 326.²⁷ Nothing is known of Philotas of Augaia.²⁸

The information given by Curtius about infantry reorganization does not lend itself to clear interpretation, mainly because Alexander's infantry after 331 still included units called both *taxeis* (initially numbering 1,500 men each) and *chiliarchiai* (totaling 1,000 men). There is one coherent possibility to explain the new structure and increased manning of phalanx infantry units. It seems that the creation of chiliarchies must have caused a change in the strength of soldiers in battalions called *taxeis*, which had hitherto numbered 1,500 men. The average strength of the *taxeis* was raised from 1,500 to up to 2,000, divided into two *chiliarchies*. This solution was proposed by A. von Domaszewski in 1926, who claimed that each *taxis* comprised one chiliarchy of heavily armed and one of lightly armed soldiers.²⁹ Domaszewski's solution was followed by some scholars.³⁰ The hypothesis

²³ Hatzopoulos 1996, I, 447; Bosworth 1980, I, 148.

²⁴ A detailed analysis of the list gives Atkinson 1987, 419-431; he conjectures that Curtius originally listed nine names and the list "offers no conclusive evidence."

²⁵ Plut. *Mor.* 339B. Cf. Atkinson 1987, 425-6.

²⁶ Curt. 7.1.5. Cf. Berve 1926, II, no. 178; Heckel 2006, 60.

²⁷ Heckel 2006, 30-31 assumes the existence of two officers called Antigenes.

²⁸ Heckel 2006, 216 proposes an identification of Philotas of Augaia with Philotas known as officer fighting at Halikarnassos.

²⁹ Domaszewski 1926, 29-31; he dated the reform sometime before the Central Asian campaign (329-327). His assertions are not cited by Atkinson 1987, and Goukowsky 1978, I.

³⁰ According to P. Goukowsky, it was in Sittakene that the phalanx *taxeis* were each increased to the strength of 2,000 men, divided into two chiliarchies (1978, I, 255-6). Likewise, J.E. Atkinson

of Domaszewski offers the most convincing explanation of the Sittakene reforms. Other attempts to explain the reorganization are not persuasive. Thus, N.G.L. Hammond, for example, claims that Alexander established eight chiliarchies as new task forces and used them in action against the Uxians in Persis. This hypothesis is highly speculative as it assumes that soldiers in the chiliarchies “retained their affinity with the original units,” i.e., with *taxeis* numbering 1,500 men each.³¹ It would have meant redoubling the military structure, something Alexander, who desired a clearly defined and highly efficient organizational system in the army, certainly did not contemplate.

The six reformed battalions now numbered 12,000 men. Contrary to some scholarly opinions, there is no evidence to suggest that a seventh infantry battalion was established in Sittakene.³² The reinforcements brought from Europe were too limited to enable the creation of new large units. Alexander needed 3,000 soldiers to increase his *taxeis*. The remaining 3,000 were intended to replenish the hitherto existing casualties. R.D. Milns estimates the regular phalanx losses between 334 and 331 at approximately 2,800.³³ Additionally, at Babylon, Susa and Persepolis, approximately 4,700 Macedonian garrison troops were left. Alexander received 6,000 Macedonian foot soldiers in 331. In 330 Alexander left 6,000 Macedonian troops, probably all infantry, at Ekbatana (Arr. *An.* 3.19.7). At the same time, the king kept three *taxeis*, commanded by Krateros, Amyntas and Koinos, with him (Arr. *An.* 3.23.2, 3.24.1). After the reorganization in Sittakene the battalions numbered 2,000 soldiers each, thus the total was six *taxeis* in 330.³⁴

For six enlarged *taxeis* consisting of 12 chiliarchies Alexander should have appointed 12 chiliarchs. But Curtius talks about eight chiliarchs. How can we explain this statement? Presumably, six new chiliarchs were appointed for six *chiliarchiai* in phalanx. The remaining six phalanx *chiliarchiai* were given to the former battalion commanders (*taxeis*). It remains, therefore, to explain the appointment of the two new chiliarchs. One of them must have been the commander of the archers (whose corps was enlarged), the key formation for Alexander, and the other was the commander of the elite Thracian javelineers' division.³⁵

argues that the infantry *taxeis* were raised from 1,500 to a nominal 2,000, and each new *taxis* was divided into two chiliarchies during the reforms in Sittakene (1994, II, 58-9).

³¹ Hammond 1981, 164-5. He relies on Arr. (*An.* 3.17.2) who mentions Hypaspists and 8,000 of the rest of the army as Alexander's army fighting against the Uxians. However, other figures are given in Curt. 5.3.3.

³² Domaszewski 1926, 285-6. But Berve 1926, I, 115-6, and Milns 1966, argue that the alleged seventh *taxis* was created by Alexander at Susa or in Sittakene in late 331.

³³ Milns 1966, 163-4.

³⁴ Milns 1976, 159-161 argues that 6,000 infantry in Ekbatana represented four battalions, but this view ignores the real nature of the Sittakene reorganization.

³⁵ Heckel 2016, 271 proposes that the nine high officers appointed in Sittakene were actually three chiliarchs and six pentakosiarchs (commanders of five hundred) of the Hypaspists.

The Archers and Javelin Men

The archers of Alexander's army have not yet been the subject of any detailed study,³⁶ notwithstanding the fact that they were among the army's crucial formations.³⁷ The army which took part in Alexander's Asian campaign included archers from both Macedonia (Arr. *An.* 3.12.2, 2.9.2) and Crete (Arr. *An.* 2.9.3-5, 3.12.2).³⁸ Several of their commanders were killed in combat, which proves that the bowmen were among the most active and vulnerable units. At the outset of Alexander's expedition the archers numbered about 500,³⁹ but at Gaugamela (331) they totaled about 1,500.⁴⁰ In Sittakene it seems that the units of bowmen were reinforced by fresh soldiers from Europe, both Macedonians and Greeks, and increased to the strength of 2,000 men (two *chiliarchiai*).

Curtius Rufus (5.4.14) mentions a unit of 1,000 "mounted" archers in Krateros' corps at the Persian Gates (winter 331/330). There is no other mention of mounted archers in the royal army of Alexander until the Central Asian campaign. It could thus be an error of Curtius. Polyainos 4.3.27 claims that in a mountain operation at the Persian Gates (few weeks after the reforms in Sittakene) Alexander used Hypaspists, a unit of "phalanx hoplites" and all the "Skythian archers". Polyainos must have used a garbled source for Alexander, who had no "Skythian" archers in his army until 327. Alexander must have encountered mounted archers during his Danube campaign against the Getai and Triballi in 335. The Getai had such armed units.⁴¹ But nothing is heard about mounted archers throughout Alexander's campaign until he enlisted Central Asian mounted archers in his army in 327.⁴² From a tactical point of view, mounted archers would have not been of much use for defending a fortified camp. It is possible that Curtius should have referred to foot archers. This is confirmed by Arrian 3.18.4 who mentions two infantry battalions, a few archers and about 500 horsemen left with Krateros in charge of the camp. During the same operation, Alexander had a unit of foot archers in his strike force (Arr. *An.* 3.18.5). If the figure for archers in Curtius 5.4.14 is correct, the total of archers in Alexander's army at that time must have exceeded 1,000 and was prob-

³⁶ A short analysis is given by Berve 1926, I, 131-133; Griffith in Hammond / Griffith 1979, 430-431, and Sekunda 1998, 46-48. A useful prosopographic account is offered by Heckel 2016, 227-229.

³⁷ Arrian (in the *Anabasis*) mentions Alexander's archers 52 times. Cf. Berve 1926, I, 131.

³⁸ The names of the commanders of the archers are Macedonian (Antiochos, Kleandros, Klearchos) or Cretan (Eurybotas, Ombrion), cf. Heckel 1992, 335-6.

³⁹ Diod. 17.17.4 with Berve 1926, I, 132.

⁴⁰ Sekunda 1996, 46-48 assumes three *lochoi*, i.e. 1,500 archers, at Gaugamela. Devine 1989, 77-78 speaks of two companies called *xenagiai*, each 500 men.

⁴¹ In 335 Alexander invaded the Danube region on news of unrest among the Triballi. These were defeated in two battles (Arr. *An.* 1.1.8-13, 1.2.3-7; Plut. *Al.* 11.5). Then the Getae north of the Danube (Arr. *An.* 1.3.5-1.4.5) were defeated. For mounted archers of the Getae, see Thuk. 2.96.

⁴² Olbrycht 2004, 168-171.

ably 2,000. The corps of archers was supposedly divided into *lochoi* consisting of 500 men each, and *chiliarchiai*. After Darius' defeat, the company of Cretan archers was dismissed by Alexander,⁴³ but at that time, Alexander gained large units of Iranian archers, including them into his guard detachments.⁴⁴

Alexander found out with some force at the Persian Gate just how valuable archers and other light infantry were in combat in mountainous terrain; the Persians, using thousands of archers and slingers in their ranks, were successful in repulsing Alexander's first attack. In Alexander's army, bowmen appear throughout the struggles in eastern Iran and in Central Asia (cf. Curt. 6.4.2; Arr. *An.* 3.23.2 etc.).

Alongside the archers, the key role was played by the javelineers, who were indispensable in fighting in the mountains. Famed javelin men were recruited among the Balkan peoples.⁴⁵ Alexander's favorite troops included allied Agrianes, perhaps reinforced by the fresh forces of Thracian troops to a number of about 1,000 in Sittakene. The Agrianes were a Paionian or Thracian tribe and the possible reinforcements may have been included in the Thracian corps named in the sources. The Agrianes were commanded by the Macedonian Attalos.⁴⁶

In the operation in Uxian country in winter 331/330 there was a unit of 1,000 Thracian infantry, i.e. a *chiliarchia* of javelin men - *akontistai*. It could be part of a 2,000-strong battalion (*taxis*) of javelin men or an independent unit, just like Agrianes. In many later battles fought by Alexander, one can hear about Thracian javelin men in the riskiest operations, including the battle at the Hydaspes. It can be assumed that the select Thracian javelin men surpassed 1,000: in all likelihood they numbered a minimum of 2,000 men (at least two *chiliarchiai*).

Conclusion

The introduction of the 1,000-strong units called *chiliarchiai* in the Macedonian army imitated the Persian army system, as units numbering 1,000 soldiers were the organizational basis of the elite formations of the Achaemenids.⁴⁷ In Sittakene, the old phalanx units – the battalions (*taxeis*) of the *pezhetairoi* and *asthetairoi* – were modified in terms of manpower. The Macedonian reinforcements allowed Alexander to raise the nominal strength of the six infantry *taxeis* from 1,500 to 2,000.

⁴³ Sekunda 1998, 46-48.

⁴⁴ Olbrycht 2004, 116-120.

⁴⁵ On the Balkan contingents in the army of Alexander, see Berve 1926 I, 133-139.

⁴⁶ Heckel 2006, 62.

⁴⁷ Achaemenid troops were organized decimally – in tens, hundreds, and thousands. See Head 1992, 17. A certain similarity to Alexander's reform exhibit changes made in the army of Cyrus the Younger who set the size of the *lochos* in his newly formed army including Greek mercenaries at 100 (Xen. *An.* 3.4.21). This reform was to replace the Greek military structure, in which units were multiples of four or six, by the Persian system formed on a decimal basis. See Lee 2004.

The subdivision into chiliarchies applied not only to the Hypaspists and line Macedonian infantry (*pezhetairoi*, *asthetairoi*), but also to some other units which were to play a crucial role in the new theater of operations, i.e., in the mountains of Iran and Central Asia: archers and some units of javelineers, including the Agrianes and some Thracians. Later in the campaign, mentions are made of archers' *chiliarchiai*. In Sittakene, probably no more than 2,000 of them were present, since by then Alexander had not had a chance to recruit more of the superb Iranian bowmen.

In his Sittakene reforms, Alexander lay the foundations for his new army. The binary system predominated, i.e., two smaller units making up a larger one. Infantry units were *taxeis* (2,000 men), *chiliarchiai* (1,000 men), and companies (*lochoi* or *pentakosiarchiai*), numbering 500 men. Overall, it is a system known from the Greek *Taktika* by Asklepiodotos (2.10), reflecting the structures of Hellenistic armies. Alexander planned to make the system of 500 and 1,000 units universal throughout his entire army. This is why we repeatedly hear of units numbering 500 and 1,000 soldiers appearing in later warfare under Alexander (331-323) and in the subdivision of royal guards. At a basic level Alexander retained the old system: the smallest unit known in the Macedonian infantry under Alexander was the *dekad*, consisting of 16 men.⁴⁸

In 331, Alexander could not fully reform his cavalry, with too few new troops for his purpose. Still, they sufficed to restore or even slightly enlarge the battle strength of the Companions. It seems that the new squadrons (*ilai*) now numbered about 250 (ideally 256) men each. After Philotas was executed, by the late 330, Alexander had already introduced a formal division into two *chiliarchiai* in the Companion cavalry, each numbering about 1,000 men (Arr. *An.* 3.27.4). Often Alexander would deploy in Central Asia a force of "half the Companions" (see Arr. *An.* 3.24.1), effectively meaning a single chiliarchy. Not impossibly, the division of the Companion corps (called *taxeis*) into two *chiliarchiai* may have been introduced in Sittakene, and the reorganization in eastern Iran in 330 may have dealt with the command structure.

The key to understanding the point of Sittakene reforms are the campaigns Alexander conducted immediately afterward against the Uxians and the battle at the Persian Gates (late 331), and also further campaigns in Persis, against Darius III in Media and western Parthia as well as military operations in Hyrcania (330). In these operations Alexander used mainly light elite troops of his army. The exact list includes: Hypaspists, selected chiliarchies of the phalanx infantry (most mobile units), units of archers (Macedonians and Greek mercenaries), and Thracian javelin men, as well as Agrianes (treated as special forces) and some cavalry units.

The reorganization in Sittakene, conducted chiefly by demands of strategy and tactics, might have been inspired by the reorganization of the Persian army as

⁴⁸ Kallisthenes *FGrHist* 124 F35 (phalanx of Alexander at Issos). See Griffith in Hammond / Griffith 1979, 419-420.

described by Xenophon: Cyrus the Great introduced a reform under which Persian ranks (called *homotimoi*) were reinforced with new soldiers regardless of whether they were native Persians. The only criterion that mattered was their personal bravery.⁴⁹ Xenophon speaks also that Cyrus organized a military competition for his officers, with promotion as the prizes (*Kyr.* 2.1.23ff.). Alexander must have read Xenophon, and the latter's inspiration is likely. That is probably the source of the idea of the officers' competition. But for the king, of course, the current military requirements were more important than the theoretical recommendations of writers. The king perfectly prepared his armed forces for new challenges in Iran and Central Asia.

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⁴⁹ Xen. *Kyr.* 2.2.26, 2.1.11, 2.1.13, 2.1.9. Most scholars deny Xenophon's reliability concerning historical content of *Kyrupaideia* but a number of details, including the reform mentioned by Xenophon, may have been historical.

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Abstract

Following the subjugation of Babylonia, Alexander's next major target was Susa, one of the Achaemenid metropolises on the plains of Khuzestan, located at the gateway to the Iranian Plateau. Iran was a separate theatre of war with huge mountains, deserts and long, vulnerable communication routes. The new conditions and challenges of the planned campaign in Iran required the creation of a deeply modified armed force. Alexander urgently needed new missile troops, light infantry javeliners, and a stronger cavalry. He also had to reorganize the army to better coordinate his actions, and flexibly divide and combine strike units. To achieve these goals, Alexander decided to introduce military reforms in Sittakene, located between Babylonia and Susiana.